

Towards a Multipolar World Where Western Hegemony is Faltering

What is the possible future for the European Union?

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Abstract— *This work does not seek to trace the causes of the Russian-Ukrainian war, as it is very difficult to separate fact from fiction. When interests are at stake, everyone pulls the blanket towards themselves, and the blanket is not stretchy. There are therefore always winners and losers. In a world of geopolitical interests, seizing resources becomes a leitmotif. Added to this is ideology, where everyone believes they are right. Finally, the belligerents will always accuse each other, and propaganda is a destructive tool elevated to a degree of excellence. Artificial intelligence is also used by the protagonists to shout their message, with the possibility of spreading "fake news" relayed by complacent media, whether forced or not. In addition, beliefs and prejudices are beginning to increase, and demonization is never far away. This work presents an overview of events, with a reminder of historical facts. It is also a reflection on events and possible outcomes for the European Union, which is mired in the Russian-Ukrainian war. The confrontation between a multipolar and globalist world is crystallizing, with real risks of a large-scale war. New geopolitical confrontations are emerging. An important question arises: what is the possible future for the European Union?*

Keywords—European Union, Russia, Ukraine, Western hegemony, multipolar world, Future of the EU.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research focuses on the Russo-Ukrainian conflict and the European Union. What future awaits Europe? Using collected documents and information, this work examines the European colonial period and the formation of the USA. After a brief overview from the First World War to the present day, this work addresses the Russo-Ukrainian War, analyzing the events. Two essential questions this article attempts to answer are: why is Europe involved in this war, and what might be the future of the European Union?

II. REMINDERS FROM THE RENAISSANCE TO THE 20TH CENTURY

The West has dominated much of the world for several centuries, and more markedly since the Renaissance, in the aftermath of the Middle Ages. Expeditions such as those of Magellan, Christopher Columbus and others bear witness to this. The Renaissance was a melting pot of new scientific and military discoveries. Even the world of art exploded with new genres, new styles, new ways of dressing and living. However, the commoner remained a commoner, and in the West, the Third Estate continued to dominate until the Revolution of

1789, with the period of the "Age of Enlightenment" in France. This period was a radical change from the remnants of feudal power. It was also a struggle against the prerogatives of the Church, accompanied by expropriations, annexations and bloodshed. In this struggle during the "Age of Enlightenment", Freemasonry also played a quasi-doctrinal role. Gradually, in France and Belgium, Freemasonry became "liberal" by banning references to the divine. This was the case with important Obediences such as the Grand Orient de France and the Grand Orient de Belgique. This change in vision took place gradually and came to fruition at the end of the 19th century. The 20th century saw the decline of the Church's influence after the Second World War of 1939-1945. Secularism grew stronger and attempted to reduce the role of the Church in social life and people's daily lives. Today, some people talk about secularism becoming a new religion. Political forces attempted to transform the world, using instruments such as state pressure or dictates in certain countries, such as state communism. For example, with regard to the Church, during the communist period in the USSR, places of worship were controlled and it was not considered appropriate to attend church, but rather to have a party card. This oppression was real, since in Central and Eastern European countries, following the implosion of the USSR in 1991, places of worship began to fill up again. For example, in Poland, Hungary, Serbia and Slovakia, the Christian religion regained strength and vigour. Human beings are curious by nature and have a gregarious instinct, so sooner or later they rebel against prohibited things. Let us return to the Renaissance and its importance: buildings went from being sacred to the secular. The printing press, invented a little earlier by Gutenberg, democratized writing, which encouraged the Reformation. Cathedrals were no longer built to the glory of God, nor were minimalist, uncomfortable castles; instead, magnificent palaces were built, houses for nobles and bourgeoisie, complete with gardens. The 17th and 18th centuries gave us architectural gems such as the Palace of Versailles in France (construction began in 1623) and Schönbrunn Palace in Austria (construction began in 1742) under the Habsburgs. Kingdoms and empires began to compete in terms of the grandeur and magnificence of their buildings; even huge gardens became a sign of power, grandeur, aesthetic beauty and wealth, but also of attraction and intimidation.

III. THE EUROPEAN COLONIAL PERIOD AND THE CONSTRUCTION OF THE AMERICAN EMPIRE

Following scientific discoveries and innovations in the military field (16th and 17th centuries), Western states became explorers and colonizers of entire regions, countries and continents. A New World and unlimited territorial expansion began to emerge. Gradually, a globalist empire (the British Empire) dominated the world until its final fall in the aftermath of the Second World War to the benefit of its Western Big Brother, the United States. The USA was built either by force (against Mexico, for example) or by buying up entire regions, such as California, which originally belonged to Mexico, or by buying Alaska from the Emperor of Russia, or by buying French Louisiana. This American reflex is almost visceral: business is business! The proof is that the current US President, Donald Trump, wants to either annex Greenland by force or to buy the world's largest island for national security purposes. In reality, Greenland is an autonomous region that is part of the Kingdom of Denmark. Only time will tell whether the island's 57,000 inhabitants will be tempted by the prospect of becoming American. In reality, it is always money and resources, exploitable raw materials, that guide an expansionist state. Europe has gradually lost its colonies, for example, Algeria for France, or its hegemonic power in Africa, particularly in the Sahel countries. Other Western countries have also lost their colonial grip, for example, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, Spain, Portugal and Germany, to name but a few Western countries. During the colonial period, there was extermination of populations, slavery, displacement of populations, and the imposition of languages, for example Spanish in South America, Portuguese in Brazil, English in African countries such as South Africa and India, French in Cameroon and elsewhere, etc. The most significant extermination was undoubtedly that carried out by the Conquistadors in Central and South America, and by white Americans who exploited black people and exterminated the Indians. It should be remembered that segregation existed in the United States until the 1960s, with denunciations of the system in place spearheaded by Martin Luther King in the United States and Nelson Mandela in South Africa. The case of the United States is unique. While proudly proclaiming itself to be the pinnacle of democracy, the United States has nevertheless been the instigator of the downfall of unwelcome governments (there are hundreds of examples of pressure on other states, organized coups, interventions in the internal affairs of other states, etc.). There is a saying that "it is better to be a friend of the United States, but the United States has no friends, only interests". Henry Kissinger warned of the United States' unchallenged hegemonic behaviour.

IV. FROM THE SECOND WORLD WAR TO THE PRESENT DAY

The US helped Europe during the Second World War when Europe seemed lost and the British Empire was beginning to die. The US also intervened because it could not leave the whole of Europe to the Soviet Union of the time. Thus, Germany was divided into West Germany and East Germany. Other countries

in Eastern and Central Europe became satellite states of the USSR until 1989.

A "Cold War" ensued between the Western Bloc and the Eastern Bloc, with an arms race and the proliferation of nuclear bombs, but also throughout the world (China, India, then Pakistan, North Korea, Israel, etc.). The reunification of Germany could not have taken place without the agreement of Russia, heir to the USSR. The broken promise by the West led to NATO's expansion to Russia's doorstep. In Europe, the Balkans, Moldova and Belarus were the only countries remaining under the influence of Russia, which had been weakened in 1990-1991 following the implosion of the USSR. This was an opportunity not to be missed for the Western Bloc: without a UN mandate, the West carved up Yugoslavia, creating states and regions that became states, such as Kosovo. On 24 March 1999, NATO launched an aerial bombing campaign against Yugoslavia. But the appetite of an empire is insatiable! Another empire is trying to emerge: the European Union wants to become a kind of "United States of Europe". Anything goes when it comes to sanctioning and ostracizing from Europe any state that refuses to follow the dictates of the European technocrats in Brussels. But it is interesting to note that currently, the three leaders with the most power in the EU are three Germans (Von der Leyen, Merz and Weber): is this a balanced distribution of European power? A strong Europe becoming an empire that has subjugated sovereign countries is not to the liking of the US. Initially, to rebuild post-war Europe, the Marshall Plan was proposed on 5 June 1947 by US Secretary of State George C. Marshall at Harvard, and officially began on 3 April 1948 for a period lasting until 1952. Western countries then created the Common Market (Treaty of Rome in 1957), with the aim of creating prosperity and free movement of goods, services and people. Gradually, the Western countries of the 'Common Market of Six' accepted other European countries. The goal was certainly economic expansion and already an unproven desire for globalization. Since the European Union has 27 member countries, it is difficult to manage such a large number of countries, each of which also has a right of veto. The stated idea has become clearer: globalization and thus the desire to eliminate the sovereignty of Member States. Currently, political battles are becoming increasingly violent between globalists and sovereignists, and it seems that anything goes (blackmail, political pressure, sanctions, etc.). The major event that disrupted global wokism (originating in the US) was the election of Donald Trump, which necessitated a reshuffling of the deck. However, the European Union continued to intervene in favour of a Democrat (the re-election of Joe Biden, then Kamala Harris, to the detriment of Donald Trump). Against all odds, Donald Trump won the election and was sworn in as President in January 2025. The problem is that the current President has not forgotten the European Union's positions and opinions against him during his election campaign; moreover, he is a sovereigntist and seems to be against wokism and the NGOs of George Soros, who is a friend of the globalists. It is not for nothing that the current US President prefers heads of state such as Meloni, Fico and Orbán.

Under Joe Biden's reign, the Europeans and the US have spent or lent hundreds of billions on the Russian-Ukrainian war.

They have tried in vain to isolate Russia, to bring about its downfall, no doubt in order to break it up so that they can exploit vast, sparsely populated regions rich in mineral resources, gas, oil, rare earths, etc. However, the Western Bloc has failed to bring Russia to its knees. They have encouraged something they did not expect: the rapprochement of countries from another multipolar world. They did not foresee the results of their actions: the expansion of the BRICS, the Global South breaking away to the point of isolating the Western Bloc, not to mention certain countries in South America. These new players are coming together with the aim of preserving their sovereignty, but are increasingly favourable towards Russia. They have been hoisted by their own petard! The Western Bloc is increasingly isolated: 1 billion people against 7 billion!

V. EUROPEAN UNEASE OVER DONALD TRUMP AND THE RUSSIAN-UKRAINIAN WAR

The unease has been palpable since Donald Trump came to power.

Under Joe Biden's administration, the European Union was in perfect harmony! Joe Biden, a globalist and woke activists, gave more than \$200 billion to the Ukrainians, engaging in a hybrid war with the Europeans, who also invested in military equipment and gave/lent billions to Ukraine. The bill is steep for the European Union: to date, approximately €180 billion has been paid to Ukraine. But Donald Trump (who became President in January 2025) caused a break: his disinvestment in the Russian-Ukrainian war that began in February 2014, with Russian support in Donbass, followed by the Russian invasion of Ukraine on 24 February 2022. The European Union, dependent on American military equipment, had to purchase weapons to give to Ukraine. Recently, the European Union voted on a budget of €90 billion for Ukraine, and the Ukrainian government is already asking for an additional €800 billion for the reconstruction of Ukraine. It goes without saying that without the US, without dollars, the European Union would not be able to win the war against Russia and has no more money to give. The European Union has already had to borrow the 90 billion! Donald Trump is distancing himself from the European Union with each passing day and sees his interests elsewhere than in Ukraine (China, Venezuela, Iran, Palestine, etc.). Left to its own devices, the Union will struggle to finance the war... Doubts are creeping into people's minds: does the US want to weaken the European Union, which aspires to become the United States of Europe, by hook or by crook, by crushing the will of certain recalcitrant Member States such as Hungary, the Czech Republic and Slovakia? Wouldn't the US ultimately be better off doing business with an undefeated Russia? The European Union seems to be heading for disaster in this situation. The media has often denigrated Russia by selling assumptions as certainties. The European Union is no slouch in this regard either. In the bibliography, I propose a series of assumptions presented as facts, including:

- the soldiers no longer have weapons
- Russia is using washing machine chips
- Russian forces are using shovels as weapons
- fake news about Putin's illnesses

In addition, disinformation, withholding information, under-reporting, and demonizing Russia have been used as propaganda tools. But we must not forget that Russia is not a paragon of virtue either. Indeed, propaganda on their side has also been in full swing. Problems ahead for European Union leaders and questions that leaders will have to answer sooner or later:

- how to win the war against Russia as it builds up its military power?
- How can we explain the billions spent on the war, with no results?
- How can they explain the impoverishment of the population as a result of this war?
- What are the European Union's motivations for continuing this war?
- How can the increase in the cost of living, food prices and energy costs be justified?
- How can we explain the shift from economic dependence (on Russian gas and oil) to dependence on the US?
- How can power be maintained in the current political climate and tensions?
- How can one explain having given unconditional support to a corrupt country?

VI. WHAT IS THE POSSIBLE FUTURE FOR THE EUROPEAN UNION?

As the saying goes, 'A fault confessed is half forgiven!'

The European Union made a mistake in thinking it could indefinitely cut itself off from Russia and its trade ties. It has become completely dependent on the US and risks becoming increasingly isolated, not to mention a very uncertain future for its people due to political errors. The European Union should be more incisive towards a corrupt country (Ukraine) that wants to join the European Union. The Union should be more unifying and respect the sovereignty of Member States instead of doing everything at any cost to become a "superstate" where countries could become mere provinces, as in the Roman Empire. The European Union should be closer to its citizens for greater transparency. It will be very difficult for European Union politicians to justify to the public the hundreds of billions needed for Ukraine to continue the war. The Union should eradicate all forms of corruption within its ranks through concrete and radical action. The European Union should free itself from the grip of the US, which seems to be much worse than simple dependence on Russian gas and oil. The European Union wants to continue an economic war with Russia, believing that Russia cannot sustain the war for long. This is a miscalculation, extremely risky in the face of a nuclear power. All this for a country rife with corruption and where human rights are violated and which is becoming increasingly autocratic. The European Union should reopen dialogue with Russia to get trade relations off to a good start. This is more problematic, as the US has done everything it can to kill off any possible relations with the European Union. The US has always feared the economic development of the European Union, and an economic alliance between Europe and Russia would have propelled the European Union to the top in terms of GDP. The

European Union should stop practising the political technique of "double standards" in order to regain its credibility on the world stage. In addition, the feelings of certain African countries, which consider that Westerners often behave in a neo-colonialist manner, should be taken into account. Frank dialogue would be necessary to restore confidence. As the current occupant of the White House does not seem to have any regard for Europeans and is incapable of engaging in dialogue on equal terms, the European Union should find a new path forward that involves autonomy from the US.

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